

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It is my pleasure to announce the 14th and last regular issue of this year. I want to take the opportunity to gratefully thank all institutions and individuals - including the consortium members, members of the editorial board, the editorial and technical team, as well as the authors - for all their support and effort to make J.UCS one of the high quality journals in computer science. In this issue we have 5 papers contributed by 16 authors from 5 countries.

The authors Itziar Arrieta-Salinas, José Enrique Armendáriz-Iñigo and Joan Navarro from Spain present a distributed storage architecture, called Epidemia, featuring a hybrid approach that combines classic database replication with a cloud-inspired infrastructure to provide transactional support and high availability.

A model-based approach to the design and verification of motordrive software for networked motion control systems is presented in a Korean research work by Youngdong Kim, Ikhwan Kim, Inhye Kang, Taehyoun Kim, and Minyoung Sung.

The authors Xinyu Li, Xiaoyu Wen, and Liang Gao from China propose in their work an effective genetic algorithm to optimize the multi-objective integrated process planning and scheduling (IPPS) problem with various flexibilities in process planning.

Michał Pańczyk and Halina Bielak from Poland investigate in their research work a self-stabilizing algorithm for locating the center of maximal outerplanar graphs.

Tapio Soikkeli, Juuso Karikoski and Heikki Hämmäinen from Finland propose a context classification framework that aims to clarify the use of the term context in handset-based related end user studies to be used for more personalized mobile services and user experiences.

Enjoy reading!

Cordially,

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